

Diversity **E**quity **I**nclusion

Short-Case Series

Fostering diversity and inclusion by making jewelry from trash: The power of a single entrepreneur

Case theme: raising awareness on DEI issues in SMEs

CASE: Fostering diversity and inclusion by making jewelry from trash: The power of a single entrepreneur

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Abstract

[Matti Mattsson](#) – internationally renowned and nationally awarded circular jewelry artist calls himself a crazy Finn and has an amazing story to share. Through his small business he has transformed the life of many people, fostering diversity and inclusion when sourcing for his business, when providing services and building international relations, and when practicing unique marketing ideas directed not only at increasing business growth and profitability, but also when addressing needs of different social groups, such as older people, children with behavioral concerns, and people with disabilities. This teaching case invites us to explore the concepts of diversity (representation of various social identity groups) and inclusion (creating an environment that offers appreciation for diverse needs, perspectives, and experiences) through a lively story of an entrepreneur. The story shows that even a single person managing a small business can make a large social impact and foster socially sustainable business and community environment.

Key words: diversity, inclusion, circular economy, circularity, age, disability, international partnerships, micro enterprise

Case relates to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals:

- 10 (Reduced inequality),
- 11 (Sustainable cities and communities),
- 12 (Responsible consumption and production)

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1. Coming to the right place at the right time to receive The Order of the White Rose of Finland from the President

We entered through the doors of an old wooden house located in Kuopio Kortteli Museum. In the room full of useless old things, we saw a man carefully concentrating on making something with his tools from broken materials. One would think this was a repair shop, but some very weird items caught our eye:

“Sorry, *what are these shoes about?*”- we asked.

“*You know, one day, I received a letter inviting me to meet the President of Finland. In that letter, it was strictly written that I should come to the right place at the right time. To be sure that I come to meet the President as expected, I made these shoes – with a compass in one shoe and a clock in the other. When I came to the Presidential Palace, people were looking at my shoes and not that much at me.*” – answered Matti Mattsson, a single entrepreneur and a widely known artist who we were honored to meet.

(Shoes made by [Matti Mattsson](#). Photo by Aušrinė Šilenskytė)

Matti continued: “*My girlfriend convinced me to go back to school after I dropped out as a teenager and then told me to start making jewelry. When I was at Goldsmith school, at some point they wanted to kick me out, because I was not following the rules. I did exactly this work. This comes from the time I was a kid and lived with my parents when I learned that we could remake things in the house, fix things.*”

Looking more carefully around, we soon started recognizing diplomas, several recognitions, books with artist collections in which Matti was featured. It took a short while to learn that Matti’s works and jewelry have been exhibited across Finland, Italy, the USA, Germany, Spain, France, Sweden, Norway, and many other countries—where audiences shared his excitement for transforming discarded materials into art, including high appreciations by art historians and collectors, such as Nichka Marobin. Matti was also teaching art in the USA (Kansas) closely interacting with diverse students and now fostered diverse community here in Kuopio.

2. Bringing the new life to the old

After a few moments of extremely interesting conversation, it appeared that Matti has engaged with the entire community of about 100 people living in Kuopio and around Finland to ensure

that he never runs out of materials to work on. He sourced materials for his work - old or broken things that otherwise have no more value - through old people who brought these materials to him. Matti's 'suppliers' were old, but they enjoyed looking at how Matti transformed the old for the new life living this transformation together.

“They ask me: Matti – tell us what do you need? And they bring it. Then, they come to see what I did with it. Or they even send things to me by post! There was one lady, I made for her one decoration with her favorite color. She was so happy. And then, I made jewelry from the old coffee maker – I was thinking, how will they receive this in Italy, because recycling is not common there? Many young artists came around me, asked to show how I did it “

(Jewelry made by [Matti Mattsson](#). Photos by Aušrinė Šilenskytė)

3. Seeing beyond the problem

“...and my doors were always open. When I established my first workshop, some kids came and were throwing stones at my windows. They were a small gang, came to do something bad. I called them – ‘if you stop throwing stones, I teach you to make jewels. Come, I show you.’ They listened, came and they were trying, learning, I was showing them sometimes how to do it better. After they would come and protect me and my workshop from others. They even protected me from one thief... We must be brave when we meet others, and trust that it will be okay.”

Matti as a part of his entrepreneurship activities has conducted multiple workshops, especially for young people with behavioral concerns, traumatized kids or kids with various mental disabilities. He has worked with organizations, such as [Pelastakaa Lapset](#), making workshops with the children who have been psychologically traumatized or have some cognitive or developmental disability:

“I don’t care what they have. I put them to work... For example, there was one boy, they told me that he had problems with concentration after his parents got divorced. I gave him a metal plate and asked him to focus on working on it. And he was so surprised that he could focus. Until now I know that the boy likes doing things with his hands successfully and he can concentrate.”

4. The joy of concentration, not just consumption

Hearing the story about the boy and how he managed to concentrate on a metal plate, we remembered our joy when Matti offered to pick a coin made on the year we were born from the bowls with coins in the center of his workshop. The coins were the reason why we decided to return to the workshop soon after leaving and buy one piece of art from Matti. On the return journey, out of curiosity, we asked why Matti has the coins and why he offers people to pick them:

“I started this during covid pandemic. My workshop doors were open for fifty-one years, all the time I meet people from around the world and I feel in what mood people come. In the covid, these few people who would come in were very worried. Later war in Ukraine happened and people got

even more worried. There are so many things that worry people today. But when they focus on finding the coin, they must read small letters and concentrate, and so they enter the oasis of joy and peace for at least 5 minutes. Children pick the coin for luck, because coins made the year the kids were born are not yet in recycling. Old people bring coins, and then I ask visitors to pick them when they come here. Visitors also sometimes explore what else do I have here, but I want to make people feel good, not just buy things.”

(Photo: Coins to pick. Photo by Aušrinė Šilenskytė)

About Matti Mattsson

Matti Mattsson is a Finnish metalsmith renowned for his innovative use of recycled materials in art. With an international career spanning over four decades, Mattsson has transformed everyday objects into artistic creations, reflecting both environmental consciousness and creative ingenuity. Mattsson's work is deeply rooted in the principles of recycling and sustainability.

He considers metalsmithing a service occupation and maintains an open studio policy, inviting the public to engage with his creative process. Community members often contribute materials, such as old toys and household items, which Mattsson repurposes into new artworks. This collaborative approach not only breathes new life into discarded objects but also fosters a sense of community involvement in the artistic process. Throughout his extensive career, Mattsson has showcased his work both in Finland and [internationally](#). He has participated in various exhibitions, including collaborations with other artists, where his unique pieces have been displayed. Currently, Mattsson's workshop is located in Kuopio, Finland, where he continues to create and exhibit his art.

Visit Matti's website: <https://matticrazyfinn.wixsite.com/mattimattsson/>

Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/matti_mattsson_workshop/

Youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/@mattimattsson8623>

(Matti Mattsson in his workshop. Photo by Aušrinė Šilenskytė)

Questions for discussing the case

1. What diversity dimensions are visible in the case? How does Matti identify with these dimensions and/or represent them?
2. How is diversity visible in different stakeholders with whom Matti interacts? How does he address or engage with the diversity of the stakeholders?
3. Identify specific acts of inclusion Matti has implemented. Critically evaluate whether these actions primarily benefit his business, community, or both, providing evidence from the case to support your arguments.
4. How would you evaluate Matti's business: is it a private entrepreneur or a social business? Why do you think so?
5. In your environment, please find stories about smaller businesses who also address different dimensions and create acts of inclusion. Discuss them and compare them with Matti's case.
6. How does Matti's approach to sourcing and creating art contribute to the goals of a circular economy and social sustainability?
7. Reflect on the potential challenges Matti might face when scaling his approach to diversity and inclusion in a larger organizational context. How could these be managed?
8. Read about the [United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals 10, 11, and 12](#) and discuss, which specific targets of these goals are visible in this case.

(Clock made by [Matti Mattsson](#). Photo by Aušrinė Šilenskytė)